

Studies on ion exchange properties and different thermodynamic parameters of naturally occurring mixed oxides

R. K. Ghatuary^{*a}, Alok Kumar Mukhopadhyay^a and C. K. Sarkar^b

^aSuri Vidyasagar College, Suri-731 101, India

^bDepartment of Physics, B. E. College (D.U.), Shibpur, Howrah-711 103, India

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Locally available 'China Clay' a mixed oxide of aluminium, silicon, titanium and iron is thermally stable and possesses both cation as well as anion exchange capacity. Thermodynamic parameters have been calculated on the basis of distribution coefficient values of some cations and anions for the exchange process with the exchangers.

Among the synthetic inorganic ion exchangers, hydrated oxides of metals are reported to have both cation and anion exchange capacity at different pH¹.

We have processed a naturally occurring clay minerals of the mixed oxides of silicon, aluminium, iron and titanium which have a good ion exchange capacity, thermal stability and can tolerate inorganic and organic solvents upto appreciable concentration. From the knowledge of the values of entropy, enthalpy and free energy change of different metal ions for the exchange process many cations as well as anions may be successfully separated from their mixtures.

Results and Discussion

Heat treatment : The exchangers (~0.5 g) were heated from 200 to 800° for 1 h. The percentage of weight-loss remained constant (13.3%) in the temperature range 600–800°. The material did not show any colour change even upto 800°. Hence the weight-loss is entirely due to the loss of water molecules.

Chemical stability : The solubility study of the exchanger was carried out. The exchanger was shaken with

required solvent (50 ml) for 4 h at room temperature. Silica, aluminium, titanium and iron were determined by the usual procedures^{2,3}. The solubility was also determined by refluxing the exchanger with the solvent (50 ml) for 1 h. The exchanger was found fairly stable in water, 1 M HCl, 0.5 M NaOH/NH₄OH and also stable in mixed solvent system like 20% acetic acid + n-butanol + acetone (2 : 2 : 1).

pH titration : The pH titration³ performed with HNO₃, H₂SO₄, HCl, CH₃COOH gave three breaks in titration curve indicating that the exchanger comprises trifunctional base. On titration of the acid alone there is a more rapid decrease in pH than in presence of the salt (e.g. NaNO₃). Addition of NaNO₃ releases some OH⁻ from the exchanger and this increases the pH. The titration was also carried out with NaOH and KOH. Three breaks in the curve indicate that the exchanger is trifunctional. The clay mineral behaves both as cation-exchanger and anion-exchanger. The exchange capacity for both univalent cations and anions of the exchanger was determined at different pH. The plot of ion exchange capacity against pH shows that the ion exchange capacity decreases and cation exchange capacity increases with the increase of pH. The point of intersection

Table 1. Distribution coefficient values of metal ions and anions at 38° and 15° and the corresponding thermodynamic parameters

Ion	K _d at		ΔG (erg) at		ΔH cal	ΔS (cal K ⁻¹) at	
	38°	15°	38°	15°		38°	15°
Cu ^{II}	41.68	5.05	-2308.85	-928.28	16358.93	60.025	60.025
Zn ^{II}	29.20	171.60	-2074.39	-1629.40	-13726.43	-37.47	-42.00
Fe ^{III}	581.22	273.68	-4147.20	-3473.60	8434.68	40.46	41.34
Mg ^{II}	340.00	170.80	-3608.16	-2970.28	5338.16	28.77	28.85
Mn ^{II}	78.60	33.05	-2701.52	-2005.04	6715.98	30.28	30.28
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	422.54	45.46	-3742.56	-2187.19	17288.75	67.68	67.63
Cr ₂ O ₇ ²⁻	25.06	20.44	-1993.86	-1729.58	1579.49	11.49	11.49
MnO ₄ ⁻	18.92	100.00	-1819.97	-2639.78	-12905.45	-35.64	-35.64
SCN ⁻	4.50	47.10	-931.00	-2208.18	-18200.78	-55.53	-55.53

(isoelectric point) is at pH 5.4. The ion exchange capacity was determined at different molarity of NaCl at different pH. It was found that cation exchange capacity with respect to Na^+ ion at pH 8.5 is 1.60 mequiv./g of exchanger and anion exchange capacity with respect to Cl^- ion at pH 3.5 is 0.81 mequiv./g of the exchanger.

Distribution coefficient : Values of distribution coefficient of the metal ions were determined by batch process. The exchanger (0.5 g) mixed with metal ion solution (50 ml) was shaken for 2 h and the distribution coefficient values were measured at two different temperature 38 and 15 ($\pm 0.5^\circ$). The pH was maintained at 8.5 and pH of the solution after equilibrium become 5.0. Values of K_d of anions were also determined with 0.5 g of exchanger and 50 ml of anion solution at the above temperatures. The mixture was shaken for 2 h and pH of final solution was 3.5. For the K_d values of metal ions and anions, the thermodynamic parameters, viz. ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated. The metal ions were found to have negative ΔG values, but only metal ion Zn has negative values of ΔS and ΔH under identical conditions. It is interesting to note that ΔS values for all metal ions are temperature independent. Negative values of ΔH indicate less exchange efficiency, whereas positive values high exchange efficiency. The more the value of ΔS , the more is the spontaneity of the exchange process. Negative values of ΔG also indicate the spontaneous nature of the exchange process. Again for anions, ΔH and ΔS for $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ are positive

whereas those values for MnO_4^- and SCN^- are found negative. It is also interesting to note that for MnO_4^- and SCN^- , the K_d value increases with the decrease of temperature, indicating that at low temperature it is more absorbed. Thus the knowledge of the values of these thermodynamic parameters provides important information in separation chemistry of metal ions by ion exchange process.

Experimental

pH was measured on a LI-10 instrument. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Clay minerals obtained from Patelnagar (District Birbhum, West Bengal) was washed several times with de-ionised water and dried at 100° for 2 h. It was then ground to 200–250 mesh. The sample (0.5 g) was dissolved in 6 M HCl, heated to 100° and the solution made upto 250 ml. Iron, aluminium, titanium and silica were determined gravimetrically². The sample was found to contain 45.7% silica, 36.6% alumina, 2.6% titanium oxide and 1.3% ferric oxide.

References

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